

Next-generation of Energy Performance
Assessment and Certification

D1.9 Impact monitoring final report

Task 1.6 Impact measurement and monitoring
WP1 Project management

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the estimated impacts of crossCert, including the methodology used for the estimation and the values obtained. It is the outcome of Task 1.6, which focuses on impact measurement and monitoring and follows the interim report (D1.8), delivered in Month 18.

The impacts can be categorised into two main types: those aimed at enhancing energy certification methodologies and those related to promoting the energy renovation of buildings. The estimated values for both types of impacts of crossCert align with the expectations outlined in the Grant Agreement.

CrossCert has produced a wealth of results, guidelines, insights, recommendations, and tools available to the EPC community in each participating country (and other EU Member countries). These resources will assist in improving energy certification methodologies. Additionally, crossCert's outcomes can aid public administrations in implementing the new provisions of the EPBD recast. As an indirect result, these findings will also contribute to promoting the energy renovation of buildings.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context and scope

The primary objective of this document is to present an evaluation of the impacts of the crossCert results. This report is a follow-up to deliverable D1.8, which outlined the methodology to be used in estimating the impacts of crossCert.

This deliverable will provide details on the methodology used and present the estimated impacts. The impacts achieved by a project depend on the project's results, the dissemination of these results, and the context of the project, which may change over time.

The main change in the context of this project has been the publication of the new Directive on the Energy Performance of Buildings (Directive 2024/1275) – EPBD recast. It introduces changes not only in the energy certification of buildings but also in tools and procedures related to energy certificates, such as energy certificate databases or building renovation passports.

This change in context influences the impacts of the crossCert project. Initially, the expected impacts of crossCert were aligned with those defined in the Grant Agreement. These impacts are as follows:

- Primary energy savings triggered by the project
- Investments in sustainable energy triggered by the project
- Increased convergence of good quality and reliable energy performance assessment and certification and uptake and compliance with EU Directives and related standards
- Increased rate of application and compliance of EPCs and independent control systems with the provisions of EU and national legislation, in a defined region
- Increased convergence of training requirements and certification procedures for experts working on EPCs
- Increased integration of inspections and energy audits in the EPCs
- Reduction of the performance gap
- Additional market value of the building (single unit) with better EPC class
- Jobs generated

The publication of the EPBD recast expands the influence of the crossCert project, as the project results are valuable for implementing many of the new provisions in this Directive. Consequently, we have added a new impact:

- Contribution to the implementation of the new Energy Performance Directive on Buildings and to the concepts of next-gen EPCs

Other impacts of crossCert include the harmonisation of energy certification of buildings across EU Member States and the enhancement of the reputation of energy certificates. However, these impacts are considered to be implicitly included in the impacts indicated above.

1.2 Expected impacts

The expected impacts of crossCert, as outlined in the Grant Agreement, are detailed in Table 1. Additionally, as mentioned earlier, a new impact (number 10) is included related to the contribution to the implementation of the EPBD recast.

Table 1. Expected impacts of crossCert

Expected Impacts				
Number	Impact	Quantification		Measurement unit
		Within project duration	5 years after project end	
01	Primary energy savings triggered by the project	165.0	735.0	GWh/year
02	Investments in sustainable energy triggered by the project	364	5733	million EUR
03	Increased convergence of good quality and reliable energy performance assessment and certification and uptake and compliance with EU Directives and related standards	37.0	60.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
04	Increased rate of application and compliance of EPCs and independent control systems with the provisions of EU and national legislation, in a defined region	37.0	60.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
05	Increased convergence of training requirements and certification procedures for experts working on EPCs	37.0	60.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
06	Increased integration of inspections and energy audits in the EPCs	37.0	60.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
07	Reduction of the performance gap	37.0	60.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
08	Additional market value of the building (single unit) with better EPC class	37.0	60.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
09	Jobs generated	6552	103194	Number of full-time equivalent jobs
10	Contribution to the implementation of the new Energy Performance on Buildings Directive and to the concepts of next-gen EPCs	37.0	60.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results

As shown in Table 1, two types of impacts are distinguished.

Impacts number 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08 and 10 evaluate the improvement of energy certificate methodologies due to the crossCert results. The impact is quantified as the building stock of the EU reached by the crossCert results. Thus, in the short term, crossCert results are expected to impact the EPC methodologies of the countries participating in the crossCert consortium (whose building stock is 37% of the buildings in the EU28). In 5 years after the end of the project, the impact of crossCert in EPC methodologies is expected to reach EU Member States that account for 60% of building stock in the EU28.

Impacts number 01, 02 and 09 evaluate an indirect impact of crossCert. These impacts assess the promotion of the energy renovation of buildings thanks to the improvement of the energy certification methodologies achieved due to crossCert results.

Considering the different nature of the impacts, the evaluation methodology will be different as well.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The following section describes how crossCert's impact on improving certification procedures has been assessed. It details the contributions of crossCert to each of the impacts (03-08 and 10) and includes figures related to disseminating results. By considering both the contributions and their dissemination, an estimate of the impact of crossCert on the specified aspects (03-08 and 10) is provided.

Following this, the methodology and estimation of crossCert's impact on the energy renovation of buildings are presented. This section describes the model developed for the estimation, including input data and assumptions, as well as the results obtained.

Finally, the conclusions regarding the impacts achieved by crossCert are included.

2 Impact on the improvement of energy certification methodologies

2.1 Methodology

The methodology for assessing the crossCert impacts was outlined in the previous deliverable D1.8, the Impact Monitoring Interim Report. This methodology involves presenting the results that contribute to each impact and then demonstrating that these results are accessible to the relevant entities responsible for designing the EPC procedures in each Member State, as well as to the EPC stakeholders (such as the administration, EPC issuers, real estate sector, and building owners).

crossCert has taken an integral approach to the energy certification of buildings. This approach has involved a detailed analysis of the current energy certification and new proposals, identifying problems with the current methodologies and proposals, proposing solutions, and identifying best practices. The information obtained from this analysis is then used to develop guidelines and recommendations for improving the current certification process.

Furthermore, the certification process has been treated comprehensively. According to the crossCert criteria, improving energy certification cannot be achieved by making isolated improvements in aspects of certification such as data input or calculation models. Any modifications must consider the impact on the rest of the certification processes and stakeholders. For example, applying a new, more complex calculation model must consider whether EPC issuers are adequately trained to use it and whether EPC users will find the information provided by the new model valuable and be willing to pay the extra cost.

As a result of this methodology, crossCert has identified good practices and developed a set of adaptable recommendations and guidelines for improving energy certification, considering the specific context of each country. These contributions address the impacts outlined in the Grant Agreement. Due to the application of this methodology, the results that contribute to the impacts are in various deliverables, in some cases, belonging to different WPs.

We now detail the results that contribute to each impact. Then, we provide information on the dissemination of these results, and finally, we assess the achievement of the impacts.

2.2 Impact 03: Increased convergence of good quality and reliable energy performance assessment and certification and uptake and compliance with EU Directives and related standards

CrossCert aims to contribute to high-quality and reliable certification that adheres to EU Directives and related standards. The following results contribute to this impact:

1. **Extended conclusions and lessons learned presented in Deliverable 2.5**, which covers cross-testing data from existing EPCs. The report highlights conclusions, recommendations, lessons learned and best practices across various aspects of energy certification:
 - Simulation models (static, dynamic or calibrated models)
 - Default values
 - Indicators and scales
 - EPC recommendations
 - Performance Gap
 - Robustness of the EPC Method
 - EPC Databases
 - EPC format

- Training of EPC issuers.

These aspects significantly influence the quality and reliability of certification results, including performance gap and robustness. Furthermore, the comparison of methods from different member countries facilitates the convergence of certification methods' quality and reliability through the sharing and adoption of best practices.

2. **Testing results and conclusions from the cross-testing of the first generation of new EPCs presented in Deliverable 2.6.** This report presents the current status, recommendations, and best practices related to the proposals made by the U-CERT, QualDeEPC, and X-tendo projects. These proposals focus on various aspects of energy certification that enhance the quality and reliability of certification.

- EPC report format and contents
- Smart Readiness Indicator
- Comfort Asset Rating Procedure
- Renovation recommendations for improved energy efficiency
- Regular training
- EPCs in advertising and sales

The examination of the current state of energy certification in the above aspects uncovered non-compliance with the previous EPBD guidelines in the areas of renovation recommendations and the use of EPCs in advertising and sales. Identifying non-compliance and offering recommendations to comply EU Directives provisions aims to support adherence to EU Directives regarding energy certification. Renovation recommendations, in particular, play a crucial role in achieving high-quality certification.

3. **Results and summary of testing results presented in Deliverable 2.7 (Cross testing data (results) from the second generation of new EPCs.** Recommendations and best practices are provided concerning the suggestions put forth by the E-DYCE, EPC RECAST, D²EPC, ePANACEA, EUB-SuperHub, TIMEPAC, and iBRoad2EPC projects, focusing on relevant aspects for the next generation of energy certificates:

- Obtaining energy data for certification
- Data integration in energy certification
- Use of BIM technology
- Operational rating
- Asset rating
- Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)
- Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
- Financial Indicators
- Building Renovation Passports
- New services: alerts, notifications, performance forecasts
- Performance benchmarking, WebGIS tool
- Transition to next-generation EPCs

This deliverable offers a comprehensive overview of these elements in the upcoming generation of energy certifications, based on input and knowledge from our partners. It provides valuable insights for shaping the transition from current energy certification to the next generation of energy performance certificates for buildings.

4. **Building benchmark repository.** Having access to building data for testing and validating energy performance models can enhance the quality and reliability of energy certificates by improving the accuracy of these models.

5. **Analysis of new scales and KPIs presented in Deliverable 3.3.** This report examines the use of KPIs in partner nations such as Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Greece, Malta, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and the UK (Scotland), and classifies the KPIs. It concludes by recommending suitable output metrics and KPIs to align with the new requirements of the Next-Gen EPCs. The information in this report is valuable for complying with the EPBD recast regarding the incorporation of new KPIs in energy certificates.
6. **Analysis in Deliverable 3.4, titled "Cross-country comparison of format and nature of recommended improvements in different EPCs".** This analysis examines the presentation format of recommendations in EPC documents, the origin and nature of these recommendations, as well as the information and indicators provided. Furthermore, it delves into the assessors' role in offering these recommendations and explores potential discrepancies between assessor training and educational background, and the knowledge necessary to make appropriate recommendations. The insights presented in this report are invaluable for enhancing the quality of renewal recommendations in current energy certificates, which are a crucial component of certification.
7. **Deliverable D3.7, titled "Multi-criteria Grading of Proposed Innovations for Use in Next-Generation EPCs".** This report presents a comprehensive set of criteria for evaluating certification systems. These criteria are relevant to both current certification systems and the upcoming generation of energy certificates. It is important to note that having a unified framework for evaluating and comparing certification systems is instrumental in fostering the alignment of quality and reliability of the certification systems.
8. **Deliverable D5.2, titled "Report on EPC design and user experience".** This report presents research conducted at crossCert on the robustness and reliability of input data used in EPC assessments and of the outputs obtained. It has been observed that, in general, EPC issuers trust the input data more than the results of the EPCs. Specifically, EPC issuers consider assumed data related to the actual operation of the building (e.g., occupancy, activity) to be the least reliable data. However, variations in this perception have been noted based on the country. These findings are important for enhancing the reliability and quality of certification procedures. Furthermore, this report contains the outcomes of a workshop in which various EPC stakeholders (building users and architects, EPC assessors, and policy experts) selected their preferred options for the information displayed in the certificate (metrics, recommendations, etc.) and the format in which it is presented. The selections varied among the different stakeholder groups. The insights gathered from this workshop are valuable for achieving higher quality and reliable EPCs.
9. **Deliverable D5.4, titled "Report on promotion and marketing of EPC (Energy Performance Certificate) products and services".** This report presents research from a marketing and service promotion perspective regarding the limited popularity of energy certification and its impact on building energy renovation. Based on this analysis, recommendations are provided to enhance the perception of energy certificates and to develop effective communication and promotion campaigns for building energy renovation. Enhancing the current standing of energy certificates is crucial for establishing their credibility among users and stakeholders.
10. **Deliverable D5.5, titled "Towards people-centred EPCs: Guidelines and recommendations for development of people centred EPC and services".** This report presents the main results of Task 5.5, which are four crossCert infographics:
 - EPC Journey, mapping the process of creation of the EPCs.
 - EPC Design, guides the reader's thought through stages of Design thinking, tailored to the specific case of designing EPC Products and Services.
 - EPC Assessor's Journey, mapping the career path of certified EPC Assessors.
 - EPC Promotion and Marketing, mapping the crossCert approach to promotion and marketing of all things EPC.

The infographics serve as visual representations of various aspects of the EPC System, particularly those that have the potential to improve people-centered design. Created in

collaboration with a professional designer, these infographics are designed to facilitate a structured analysis and evaluation of existing EPC Systems. They are beneficial for individuals with varying levels of expertise, offering a clearer understanding of the EPC System and the diverse roles within it. EPC professionals can use them to break down the EPC system into logical components and promote enhancements to existing systems. Additionally, the infographics can be utilised as promotional materials to raise public awareness about the importance of EPCs, as educational tools for those teaching EPC-related subjects, or as workshop materials for EPC-related workshops. These infographics, which will be translated into the languages of the crossCert participating countries, also contribute to this impact.

11. **Deliverable D6.5, titled "Harmonisation guidelines report"**. This report provides guidelines and recommendations for harmonising EPC procedures across the Member States of the European Union, contributing to the improved quality and reliability of EPC procedures in Europe.

2.3 Impact 04: Increased rate of application and compliance of EPCs and independent control systems with the provisions of EU and national legislation, in a defined region

The crossCert project has contributed to these impacts with the following results:

1. **Analysis of the EPC recommendations and EPCs in advertising and sales included in Deliverable 2.6, titled "Cross-testing data (results) from the first generation of new EPCs"**. Current status and best practice were studied related to energy certificate recommendations and their inclusion in real estate advertisements and property transactions across crossCert countries. It was found that EPC recommendations do not fully comply with the previous EPBD (Article 11) in any of the crossCert countries. Similarly, the requirement to include certification in real estate transactions is only partially met in most crossCert countries. The deliverable also provides measures and best practices to promote compliance with EU and national legislation for both elements of certification.
2. **Deliverable 3.6, titled "Proposed harmonised verification framework for quality checking EPC outputs"**. This report proposes a harmonised verification framework for quality checking EPC outputs. The report provides an overview of current quality check mechanisms and highlights differences across crossCert countries. It aims to facilitate the harmonisation of EPC quality check measures across European countries by discussing aspects of EPC assessment approaches related to quality check methodologies. The proposed framework considers differences in EPC calculation methodologies, software, documents, energy efficiency recommendations, and qualifications requirements for EPC assessors. It provides a pathway for harmonising quality control mechanisms across all methodologies. The report also emphasises the importance of assessors' qualifications in delivering energy efficiency recommendations, based on the level of standardisation of recommendations in a methodology. The approach to recommendations in a country helps determine which quality control mechanisms are best suited to their methodology's needs.

2.4 Impact 05: Increased convergence of training requirements and certification procedures for experts working on EPCs

The training of EPC issuers is a recurring topic in crossCert. Here are the key results contributing to this impact:

1. **Deliverable 2.5, titled "Cross-testing data (results) from existing EPC"**, shows the impact of training on EPC quality, especially regarding performance, robustness, and recommendations. It

also highlights the complexity of some calculation software and the lack of guidelines and manuals to facilitate the use of these EPC software.

2. **Deliverable 2.6, titled "Cross-testing data (results) from the first generation of new EPCs"**. This report includes the assessment of the proposal for regular training for EPC issuers and provides findings and recommendations on the usefulness, design, and potential adverse effects of such training.
3. **Deliverable D3.4, titled "Cross-country comparison of format and nature of recommended improvements in different EPCs"**. This report highlights the inconsistency between EPC methodology and the training of EPC issuers in some crossCert countries. It points out that some countries rely on assessors with individual expertise, leading to low training requirements for EPC issuers and potentially compromising the reliability of the recommendations provided.
4. **Deliverable D5.3, titled "Report on training and education services for certified EPC issuers"**, presents results and recommendations based on information collected in previous deliverables and consultations with stakeholders in the context of Task 5.3, "Research on training and education of certified EPC issuers". This report offers suggestions for enhancing national training programs for EPC issuers and, in some instances, refining the training content. While many of these suggestions are specific to individual countries, several recommendations emerged that hold relevance across multiple countries.
5. **Deliverable D5.5, titled "Towards people-centred EPCs: Guidelines and recommendations for development of people centred EPC and services"**, focuses on guidelines and recommendations for the development of people-centred EPCs. One of the infographics maps the career path of certified EPC Assessors, providing insights into the needs of EPC issuers and challenges faced by EPC Assessors and Public Administrations regarding the training of EPC issuers

2.5 Impact 06: Increased integration of inspections and energy audits in the EPCs

The main deliverable contributing to this impact is the deliverable D4.4, titled "Linking next-generation of EPCs to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs", which focuses on linking the next generation of EPCs to energy audits, logbooks, and BRPs. This deliverable results from the research work carried out in Task 4.3. Additionally, deliverable D2.6 ("Cross-testing data (results) from the first generation of new EPCs) describes the current state of the integration of energy audits and EPCs across crossCert partner countries.

Through a comprehensive assessment of energy audit schemes in the partner countries and H2020 projects, crossCert (deliverable D4.4) provided recommendations and guidelines for the seamless integration of EPCs with energy audits, logbooks, and BRPs. A summary of this set of recommendations and guidelines is as follows:

- Increase the level of digitalisation by introducing new, digital tools and presenting the benefits to the energy auditor and EPC assessor.
- Increase the cooperation between different stakeholders by bringing them to the table, presenting the benefits to all parties and offering them solutions to overcome objections.
- Design dynamic energy certificates that provide not only static information but can be continuously updated. These updates could be based on insights from energy consultations, logbooks and renovation roadmaps, but also from smart meters and measurements.
- Verify and update existing information – e.g., during an energy audit. Therefore, it is advisable to increase the number of energy audits by promoting them and subsidising audit activities.
- Integrate the results of energy consultations into the energy certification process. The recommendations and analyses from energy consultations can directly contribute to the energy certificate, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of building efficiency.

- Identify the elements or tools missing in the specific country or region and choose a suitable tool from sister projects to complement the existing system, with the aim of creating a comprehensive and dynamic system that goes beyond the traditional static assessment.
- Choose useful data to be inserted in tools or to be verified or linked. Not all available data is useful. To reach the optimum of benefit and effort for analysing building data, a thorough selection of data is recommended.
- Use the opportunity of the next update of relevant guidelines, standards and laws to implement certain elements or parts of elements like next-generation EPCs, new indicators, BRPs and logbooks.
- Create framework conditions for energy audits to be used to promote the uptake of next generation EPCs, logbooks and BRPs.
- Create framework conditions and concrete processes and circumstances to allow data to be shared.
- Establish mechanisms for the continuous monitoring of energy consumption and regular updating of energy certificates. This allows timely adjustments based on implemented renovation measures.
- Introduce the obligation to report any renovation measure. This can be combined with the obligation to use a specific tool to report the measures.
- Choose a tool that focuses on tailor-made renovation measures, as they are most accepted by those responsible.
- Couple incentive systems to the implementation of renovation measures based on information from energy certificates, energy consultations and renovation roadmaps. Financial incentives can increase the willingness to carry out renovations.
- The service and processes to gain relevant data by implementing the above tools should be as automated and smooth as possible, with as few necessary steps as possible, for the end users to avoid time-consuming and thus frustrating processes for them. This is a prerequisite for the acceptance of the tools, especially by users who are not that familiar with digital services.
- Increase the interest in the energy performance of buildings among end users. In several countries, the EPC is seen as an administrative burden rather than a useful tool for the building owner or tenant. There are numerous reasons for this, but one of them is the lack of marketing of the EPC. Next-generation EPC tools, logbooks and BRPs offer valuable benefit to building owners, managers or tenants that should be communicated to increase acceptance.

In addition, deliverable D4.5, titled "EPCs as Facilitators of One-Stop Shops", offers recommendations and guidelines for the incorporation of next-generation EPCs within one-stop shops.

2.6 Impact 07: Reduction of the performance gap

Several tasks contribute to this impact. Firstly, **Deliverable D2.5, titled "Cross testing data (results) from existing EPCs", identifies the primary causes of the performance gap in the crossCert partner countries.** Additionally, it provides the leading causes of the lack of robustness of the current EPC methodologies in each member country. This identification is essential to take measures that can mitigate the performance gap. It is also observed that many of the causes are common between the different crossCert countries, such as the assumptions about building occupancy.

Deliverable D3.2, titled "Performance gap causation", provides a more detailed analysis of the results of deliverable D2.5, examining the causes of the performance gap. In addition, it assesses the performance gap in the buildings provided by the partners for crossCert and evaluates the performance gap using the methodologies employed in the countries (higher or lower level of standardisation). **Deliverable D3.5, titled "Sensitivity analysis of chosen parameters on EPC outputs", performs a numerical analysis of the effects of parameter variations and calculation approaches between methodologies on the final energy consumption values.** The results of D3.2 and D3.5 provide insights into measures and their effectiveness

in reducing the performance gap, as well as contextualising the performance gap within the objectives and functions of building energy certification.

2.7 Impact 08: Additional market value of the building (single unit) with better EPC class

According to studies cited by crossCert partners, a consistent trend is observed in most of the crossCert partners' countries: properties with higher energy ratings on their Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) tend to have higher prices. This observation underscores the increasing significance of energy efficiency in the real estate market, leading to the increase in market value for buildings with superior EPC ratings.

Key factors that enhance this impact include:

- Improved quality, reliability and credibility of EPCs
- Better integration of EPCs within the real estate sector

As detailed in previous sections, much of the work conducted by crossCert aims to enhance the quality, reliability, and credibility of EPCs and, therefore, contribute to this impact. Furthermore, **Deliverable 5.5, titled "Towards People-Centered EPCs: Guidelines and Recommendations for Developing People-Centered EPCs and Services," includes an infographic on EPC promotion and marketing.**

The integration of EPCs within the real estate sector has been primarily explored in Deliverable D2.6, titled "Cross-Testing Data (Results) from the First Generation of New EPCs", which investigates the QualDeEPC proposal concerning EPCs in advertising and sales.

In the study of this proposal, the role of EPCs in the real estate market in the crossCert partner countries was analysed. It was observed that it varies significantly from country to country, from almost irrelevant to a more significant reference document.

The cross-testing partners have identified two measures that can enhance the role of EPCs in the real estate sector (and contribute to an additional market value of buildings with better EPC class): (i) information campaigns to raise awareness about EPCs and their relevance in improving the energy efficiency of buildings, and (ii) the integration of EPCs into the financial sector by making them mandatory for obtaining preferential financing for building renovations and high-efficiency building purchases.

Concerning the integration of EPCs into the real estate sector, the proposal by QualDeEPC to establish mandatory guidelines for incorporating certificate information into commercial building transaction announcements was considered a worthwhile idea by the crossCert partners. A uniformity of style in presenting the EPC in advertisements was considered very positive.

Additionally, crossCert partners highlighted that an important aspect of guideline design is the EPC information included in the advertisement. While the inclusion of just the EPC rating is a good start, it may not provide all the necessary information. The inclusion of additional details, such as refurbishment recommendations, annual energy costs, or details of the HVAC technologies, can significantly enhance the value of the EPC for purchasers and renters (and subsequently, increase the value of higher EPC class buildings), providing them with a more comprehensive understanding of the property's energy performance.

2.8 Impact 10: Contribution to the implementation of the new Directive on the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPBD Recast) and to the concepts of next-gen EPCs

The implementation of the EPBD Recast will introduce changes to the certification procedures in each country. The results of the crossCert project will aid in applying the latest concepts of next-generation Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) in line with the new Directive.

Below, we outline the provisions of the EPBD Recast and the next-generation EPC concepts that crossCert contributes to their implementation with the outputs obtained.

Visual design

crossCert evaluated proposed formats for the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) report. **The conclusions are documented in Deliverable D2.6, titled "Cross-testing data and (results) from the first generation of new EPCs".**

One of the key conclusions was that the EPC report should be a single document to avoid duplication of tasks and reduce bureaucratic complexity. This single report should consist of a brief introductory summary of two to three pages that highlights essential information for the end user, followed by technical annexes. This approach aims to streamline the reporting process while ensuring that important information is conveyed clearly and concisely to the intended audience.

CrossCert also analysed the types and content of EPC reports preferred by different stakeholders, such as building users, architects, EPC issuers, and policy-related individuals. **A description of this analysis and the conclusions reached can be found in Deliverable D5.2, titled "Report on EPC Design and User Experience".**

One good practice noted is the format of the Danish EPC report. The new Danish report places less emphasis on the energy scale and focuses instead on proposed energy efficiency measures. The first two pages of the certificate outline these measures, detailing their economic and climate benefits, as well as practical implementation methods. Technical annexes follow these initial pages.

The introduction of online access to Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) is recognised as a beneficial practice that may lead to increased engagement from end users and a greater impact of EPCs. Online EPCs could include additional information, such as explanations of terms and concepts used in the certificate, examples of best practices, and guidance on how to implement the recommendations outlined in the certificate.

New scale of energy classes

Related EPBD Recast provision: *Art 19.2 By 29 May 2026, the energy performance certificate shall comply with the template in Annex V. It shall specify the energy performance class of the building, on a closed scale using only letters from A to G. The letter A shall correspond to zero-emission buildings, and the letter G shall correspond to the very worst-performing buildings in the national building stock at the time of the introduction of the scale.*

CrossCert has not been directly involved in addressing this issue. However, thanks to crossCert's testing methodology, we were able to compare the results of certification methodologies from different countries applied to the same building. We observed that the numerical values showed a significant deviation, but there was good agreement in the energy classes. The labels standardise the numerical values, harmonising the results across countries. This finding could potentially help redefine energy classes.

One lesson learned is that the numerical results of certificates from different countries should not be compared, as the methodologies used can vary widely. Differences may arise from assumptions about occupancy, set points, and ventilation, as well as whether different energy services are included in the calculation of energy consumption. Therefore, using numerical values from energy certifications in other countries to redefine energy ratings is not recommended.

Furthermore, the comparison conducted by CrossCert has been useful in rebutting news aimed at generating reluctance to the EPBD Recast. It was highlighted in one of our webinars, titled "**Upgrading EPCs for New Challenges: Do All EU Countries Need to Brace for the Costs of the EPBD?**" on July 13, 2023. In this session, we analysed an article from Die Welt, dated June 16, 2023, by Michael Fabricius, Lead Editor of Real Estate, which suggested that "EPCs are more demanding of buildings in certain countries". The crossCert experiment demonstrated the lack of rigour in this assertion and its inaccuracy. Consequently, the insights gained from crossCert can also help refute messages aimed at generating opposition to the EPBD recast.

These results can be found in Deliverable D2.5, titled “Cross-testing data (results) from existing EPCs”.

Common visual identity

Related EPBD Recast provision: *Art 19.3. Member States shall ensure a common visual identity for energy performance certificates on their territory.*

CrossCert has addressed this issue in two tasks: Task 2.3. Cross-testing and Task 5.2. Research on design and experience of EPC products and services.

During the execution of Task 2.3, in comparing existing Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs), the crossCert partners experienced significant problems in understanding the methodologies used by other countries due to the use of different terminology for similar concepts. For example, the EPC procedures in Austria and Slovenia use a variety of terms such as heat energy demand, energy needed for heating, energy delivered to the building, net heated volume, conditioned volume, specific site reference energy demand, net area, gross area, conditioned area, and habitable area whose definition is not always clear.

Therefore, one insight obtained was that it is essential to clarify the terms that will be used in the common EU template and ensure that these terms have a clear and consistent meaning across all countries. These results can be consulted in Deliverable D2.5. Cross-testing data (results) from existing EPCs.

Task 5.2 task ran a workshop that asked users about the visual effectiveness of different EPC designs. Two findings from that report (Deliverable D5.2. Report on EPC design and user experience) include:

1. Users are, generally, open to innovation in presenting and disseminating information but building on existing EPC formats rather than radically replacing them. Across different groups, there appears to be significant agreement on this, though with slightly more openness to new forms of information from more technical users.
2. The detail of information must be balanced with engagement to avoid information fatigue from the user perspective. The growing use of EPCs has resulted in quite diverse audiences and single, simple documents may not satisfy the needs of all those users.

Reliability and quality of EPCs

Related EPBD Recast provision: *Art 19.4 Member States shall ensure the quality, reliability and affordability of energy performance certificates.*

CrossCert has primarily focused on improving the reliability and quality of certificates for the next generation of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs). **The results of this work can be found in the following deliverables: D3.2 (titled “Performance Gap Causation”), D3.5 (titled “Sensitivity Analysis of Chosen Parameters on EPC Outputs”) and D3.6 (titled “Proposed Harmonised Verification Framework for Quality Checking EPC Outputs”).**

Additionally, during the cross-testing of existing certificates, an analysis of the causes of the performance gap and the lack of robustness was conducted. **The findings from this analysis can be found in Deliverable D2.5, titled “Cross-Testing Data (Results) from Existing EPCs”.**

One of the challenges identified with next-generation EPCs is that EPCs are required to be "reliable" across many different end-uses and applications, which can be subtly different across countries. This broader scope makes an assessment of reliability and quality control processes more difficult and diverse. For this reason, crossCert proposed a better-defined scope for EPCs that accounts for recent and proposed innovations whilst ensuring that the purpose of an EPC is consistent with original objectives. Centrally, consideration must be given to whether a deviation of purpose by country should be accommodated or if greater harmonisation should be applied. If the latter, then the divergence in method and application that already exists in country-specific EPCs needs to be considered; there is no single "European EPC", and therefore, assessments of reliability and quality will not be the same across Europe.

Affordability

Related EPBD Recast provision: *Art 19.4 Member States shall ensure the quality, reliability and affordability of energy performance certificates. Member States shall take measures to ensure that energy performance certificates are affordable and shall consider whether to provide financial support for vulnerable households.*

This is a transversal concept that has arisen when analysing most aspects of energy certification. In cross-testing exercises, affordability is a recurring theme. On one hand, low EPC prices are needed to ensure that EPCs are accessible to the entire population. On the other hand, EPC's low prices can impact their quality, as the time and effort that EPC issuers can dedicate is correlated with the price of the certificates.

crossCert offers recommendations to help reduce the time and effort required to issue an EPC (without compromising their quality). The first measure is the design of user-friendly software for issuing certificates. Automating the software operations can also decrease the time and effort needed to prepare certificates. Additionally, it was found that some EPC software used in Europe need more adequate help documentation. It complicates the tasks for issuers, increasing the efforts required for issuing EPCs.

Another recommendation from crossCert is to simplify certification procedures as much as possible to keep them affordable. More complex models or tools, such as Building Renovation Passports (BRPs) and sophisticated models (e.g., dynamic models), could be utilised after the EPC issuance—such as in energy audits or one-stop shops. These subsequent steps could be funded by the public sector.

Good practices observed in Austria and Denmark align with this approach. In these countries, energy audits are seen as a logical follow-up to energy certification, enabling end users to receive more precise recommendations. In Austria, for instance, building owners are offered funding to conduct energy audits, making these services largely free for them.

Details regarding the affordability of certification can be found in Deliverable D2.5, titled “Cross-testing data (results) of existing EPCs”, as well as Deliverables D2.6 and D2.7, which contain cross-testing data from the first and second generations of new EPCs, respectively.

New KPIs: Indoor environmental quality (IEQ)

Related EPBD Recast provision: *Art 19.5 The energy performance certificate shall include recommendations for the cost-effective improvement of the energy performance and the reduction of operational greenhouse gases emissions and the improvement of indoor environmental quality of a building or building unit, unless the building or building unit already achieves at least energy performance class A.*

CrossCert has evaluated new KPIs proposed for the next generation of EPCs in different project tasks. As an output, a set of recommendations is provided for the integration of these new KPIs in the EPCs.

Concerning the Indoor Environmental Quality, a summary of the recommendations elaborated is included next. Firstly, it is highlighted that the concept of comfort can differ between countries and understanding that this indicator (IEQ) does not necessarily correlate with energy efficiency KPIs. This must be clearly explained to end users since it may confuse them.

Moreover, several suggestions have been made to enhance the effectiveness and impact of comfort metrics in Energy Performance Certificates. It is recommended to provide end users with information about key parameters that significantly affect comfort, offering actionable recommendations for improving comfort. Including clear explanations of the synergies between the recommended energy renovation measures and the comfort metrics is also suggested. Finally, calculating new comfort scores after these measures are implemented is convenient. To avoid confusion, the comfort metrics should be represented (in the EPCs) with the same colour scales as energy efficiency KPIs.

Finally, various proposals for calculating IEQ, developed by projects within the Next-Gen EPC Cluster, have been assessed. The proposal from X-tendo has received positive feedback for its simplicity and ease of implementation in national certification systems.

Further results regarding these aspects of certification can be found in Deliverable D2.6 (titled “Cross Testing Data (Results) of the First Generation of New EPCs”), Deliverable D2.7 (titled “Cross Testing

Data: Results of the Second Generation of New EPCs”), and Deliverable D3.3 (titled “Analysis of new scales and KPIs”).

New KPIs: Life-Cycle GWP

Related EPBD Recast provision: *Art 19.2 ...For existing buildings renovated to A + class, Member States shall ensure that the life-cycle GWP is estimated and disclosed in the energy performance certificate of the building.*

crossCert has analysed the current status of this indicator’s calculation in partner countries, identifying potential barriers to its implementation in Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs). Furthermore, it has reviewed proposals for its calculation from Next-Gen EPC Cluster projects. A set of recommendations has been provided to support its integration into EPCs.

The results pertaining to this aspect of certification are available in Deliverable D2.7 (“Cross-Testing Data (Results) for the Second Generation of New EPCs”), and Deliverable D3.3 (“Analysis of New Scales and KPIs”).

New KPIs: Smart Readiness Indicator

Related EPBD Recast provision: *Art 15.3 Smart readiness of buildings. The Commission shall, after having consulted the relevant stakeholders, adopt an implementing act detailing the technical arrangements for the effective implementation of the scheme referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article, including a timeline for a non-committal test phase at national level, and clarifying the complementary relation of the scheme to the energy performance certificates referred to in Article 19.*

crossCert has analysed the current status of calculating this indicator (or similar indicators) in its partner countries. It has reviewed proposals for determining and calculating this indicator from the Next-Gen EPC Cluster projects and has developed a series of recommendations for its implementation alongside energy certification. The analysis also identified potential barriers to the success of this indicator, such as the difficulty end-users may face in understanding its meaning and value.

crossCert partners recommended conducting the SRI calculation using the same software employed for energy certification. Incorporating SRI calculations alongside EPC assessments could facilitate seamless integration. Furthermore, in considering recommendations to enhance this Key Performance Indicator (KPI) in the SRI assessment, crossCert partners suggest that these recommendations should be closely tied to improving the building’s energy efficiency and the production and management of renewable energy sources, such as solar photovoltaic (PV) systems. Additionally, global energy management—including supply, demand, and storage—along with improvements in comfort and air quality, should also be prioritised. Recommendations that focus exclusively on enhancing the SRI should be avoided.

Results related to this aspect of certification can be found in Deliverable D2.6 (“Cross-Testing Data (Results) from the First Generation of New EPCs”), Deliverable D2.7 (“Cross-Testing Data (Results) from the Second Generation”), and Deliverable D3.3 (“Analysis of New Scales and KPIs”).

Recommendations on single measures

Related EPBD Recast provision. *Art 19.5, 19.7, 19.8*

crossCert has evaluated the energy certificate recommendations across Europe and proposed improvements. One key conclusion underscores the importance of aligning these recommendations with the role of EPCs and the training of EPC issuers.

If the EPC is intended as a preliminary tool for building owners—prior to conducting an energy audit or seeking assistance from an energy assessor or one-stop shop—issuers should provide clear and concise recommendations, including estimated values. Conversely, if the EPC is designed to function as an energy audit, the recommendations must be more comprehensive and detailed. Moreover, the quality of EPC recommendations is strongly correlated with the training of EPC issuers, which must be carefully considered when designing the EPC methodology in each country.

Results pertaining to this aspect of certification can be found in Deliverable D2.6 (“Cross-Testing Data (Results) of the First Generation of New EPCs”), Deliverable D3.4 (“Cross-Country Comparison of Recommended Improvements in EPCs”), and Deliverable D5.2 (“Report on EPC Design and User Experience”).

Building Renovation Passport

Related EPBD Recast provision. *Art 12, 19.6*

crossCert is addressing the issues outlined in Deliverable D4.4 (“Linking Next-Generation EPCs to Energy Audits, Logbooks, and BRPs”). This document specifies the technical, political, and organisational requirements and recommendations for integrating next-generation EPCs and Building Renovation Passports (BRPs).

The technical integration of next-generation EPC systems with energy audits, logbooks, and BRPs necessitates a systematic approach to ensure data consistency, interoperability, and efficiency. Key recommendations include:

- Identifying missing elements or tools specific to a country or region and selecting suitable tools from related projects to complement existing systems, thereby creating a comprehensive and dynamic approach that surpasses traditional static assessments.
- Enhancing cooperation among stakeholders and increasing the level of digitalisation.
- Leveraging upcoming updates to relevant guidelines, standards, and regulations to implement features of next-generation EPCs, new KPIs, BRPs, and logbooks.
- Stimulating interest in the energy performance of buildings among end users.

Additionally, in Deliverable D2.7 (“Cross-Testing Data (Results) of the Second Generation of New EPCs”), crossCert has analysed the current status of BRPs and their integration with energy certification. This report evaluates tools and methodologies developed by projects within the Next-Gen EPC Cluster for creating BRPs and incorporating them into new EPC methodologies. It offers recommendations and identifies potential barriers to the implementation of this instrument.

Quality of the independent control system for energy performance certificates

Related EPBD Recast provision. *Art 27.1. Member States shall ensure that independent control systems for energy performance certificates are established in accordance with Annex VI, and that independent control systems for renovation passports, smart readiness indicators and reports on the inspection of heating systems, ventilation systems and air-conditioning systems are established.*

crossCert Deliverable D3.6 outlines a proposed harmonised verification framework for quality checking Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) outputs. It reviews EPC quality control procedures across Europe, situating each country's specific approach within a broader framework that defines general best practices.

This Deliverable introduces a quality control method that addresses various stages of an EPC, including calculations, software, and recommendations. It also proposes different pathways depending on choices made during these stages, such as selecting standardised versus tailored assessments. This flexible approach allows countries to implement quality control measures suited to their local context while ensuring integration within a harmonised framework. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that full harmonisation will remain limited due to the diversity of methods across countries.

Given the variations in EPC methods and frameworks among countries, quality control procedures must be adapted to national circumstances, taking into account factors such as data availability, the assessor workforce, and resource constraints. Quality control demonstrates the potential for harmonisation across multiple European countries. Rather than regulating every individual step of the process, it is more effective to harmonise overarching frameworks and objectives while identifying core principles that all countries should follow.

Validity of energy performance certificates

Related EPBD Recast provision. *Annex VI.1. Definition of a valid energy performance certificate*

Deliverables across WP3 have examined the extent and nature of differences in EPC frameworks across Europe, focusing on elements such as input usage, calculation procedures, assessor training and protocols, and the application of recommendations. **Deliverable D3.6 (“Proposed Harmonised Verification Framework for Quality Checking EPC Outputs”)**, highlights the impact of these differences on quality and deviations. Meanwhile, **Deliverable D3.7 (“Multi-Criteria Grading of Proposed Innovations for Use in Next-Generation EPCs”)**, presents a framework that may enable a more controlled approach to future innovations in EPCs.

Insights from crossCert on this topic are summarised below, offering valuable guidance for establishing the validity of EPCs. When deviations occur within a sample EPC, it is important to determine whether these arise from:

1. Country-specific approaches to EPC generation,
2. The ability or allowance for individual assessors to make independent decisions, or
3. Genuine errors by the assessor or flaws in the methodology.

Distinguishing between human errors and systemic flaws in a broader approach is crucial, as they represent fundamentally different challenges.

Certain EPC methods are more tolerant of deviations than others. For instance, frameworks that allow assessors to exercise judgement rather than relying strictly on standardised inputs (e.g., look-up tables) inherently permit some degree of deviation. While this approach may result in more tailored and actionable recommendations for building owners, it complicates cross-comparisons across the building stock.

Deviations within a country should generally be minimised, but their presence is not necessarily indicative of poor-quality control. Instead, such deviations often reflect the design considerations of the EPC framework, where the balance between standardisation and flexibility varies significantly. On the other hand, deviations between countries are more complex to analyse. Such comparisons do not always yield meaningful insights regarding the validity or suitability of different national approaches.

Databases for the energy performance certificates

Related EPBD Recast provision. *Article 22.1 Each Member State shall set up a national database for the energy performance of buildings which allows data to be gathered on the energy performance of individual buildings and on the overall energy performance of the national building stock. Such databases may consist of a set of interconnected databases. The database shall allow data to be gathered from all relevant sources related to energy performance certificates, inspections, the renovation passport, the smart readiness indicator and the calculated or metered energy consumption of the buildings covered. In order to populate the database, building typologies may also be gathered. Data may also be gathered and stored on both operational and embodied emissions and life-cycle GWP.*

crossCert has conducted an analysis of current EPC databases and the challenges they face in becoming effective tools for promoting building renovations. This analysis also evaluates compliance with the requirements of the EPBD Recast. **The findings are detailed in Deliverable D4.2 (“Analysis of the Current Integration of EPC Data”).**

This report provides several technical guidelines for improving and adding value to existing EPC database structures. These guidelines, informed by updated treatment and management of current EPCs, are categorised as follows:

- Increasing information availability: Enhancing the usability of EPC database information.
- Enhancing user interactivity: Meeting the diverse needs of stakeholders using EPC data.
- Improving interoperability: Adding value to existing repositories and EPC tools.

- Harmonising XML treatment: Establishing a common language among EU countries to improve interoperability.

Additionally, this deliverable D4.2 explores the potential benefits of EPC databases and identifies several tools compatible with EPC datasets. The following tools have been assessed as directly compatible:

- Energy indicators map: Transforming EPC data into a visual platform to inform users about the current status of the assessed stock.
- Local Renovation Roadmaps: Utilising EPC data for informed decision-making.
- Local Building Logbooks: Using EPCs as information sources.
- Smart Readiness Indicators: Employing EPCs to introduce new indicators.
- One-Stop Shops: Providing assistance through EPC databases.
- SECAPs Elaboration: Utilising EPC data for informed decisions and as data sources.

Deliverable D2.7 (“Cross-Testing Data (Results) of the Second Generation of New EPCs”), includes examples of best practices in database management. One noteworthy example is the ZEUS database in Salzburg, Austria. ZEUS (Central EPC Environment) serves as an EPC database that also integrates Building Renovation Plans (BRPs), detailed renovation measures, energy advice data, and plans. It is linked to the funding authority and inspection reports and allows integration with smart meters. Building owners can grant access to their data to selected professionals, with all services managed by a single provider, simplifying technical interfaces.

In Denmark, the Danish Energy Agency is piloting "The Building Hub," a digital platform designed to provide access to data on buildings and their energy consumption. This platform aims to integrate data from multiple sectors and databases, enhancing the quality and utility of digital EPCs.

Communication campaigns

Related EPBD Recast provision. *Article 29.1. Member States shall prepare and carry out information and awareness-raising campaigns. They shall take the necessary measures to inform the owners and tenants of buildings or building units and all relevant market actors, such as local and regional authorities and energy communities, of the different methods and practices that serve to enhance energy performance. In particular, Member States shall take the necessary measures to provide tailor-made information to vulnerable households. That information shall also be made available to local authorities and civil society organisations. Article 29.2. Member States shall in particular provide information to the owners or tenants of buildings on energy performance certificates, including their purpose and objectives, on cost-effective measures and, where appropriate, financial instruments, to improve the energy performance of the building, and on replacing fossil fuel boilers with more sustainable alternatives. Member States shall provide the information through accessible and transparent advisory tools such as renovation advice and the one-stop shops established pursuant to Article 18, paying particular attention to vulnerable households.*

crossCert has analysed the promotion and communication aspects of energy certificates, resulting in a series of guidelines and recommendations. **Deliverable 5.4 (“Report on promotion and marketing of EPC (Energy Performance Certificate) products and services”) presents this work.**

The findings indicate that positive or negative experiences, reliable technical information, and misinformation can significantly affect the perception of energy-efficient renovations. This can influence whether a renovation project proceeds or is abandoned. Effective marketing and promotion campaigns are crucial for motivating homeowners to undertake energy renovation projects. These initiatives should focus on the homeowner's lifecycle and identify key trigger points for renovation. Communication strategies must help EPC products and services gain recognition. Among these, easy-to-access and reliable media representation by governmental institutions with long-term reliable information, as well as citizen-focused promotional and communication campaigns with inspiring messages to homeowners, easy-to-understand, highly visual information stand out as particularly impactful.

Currently, EPC-related communication campaigns assume that homeowners make rational decisions based predominantly on financial factors and energy savings; consequently, EPCs are seldom mentioned. However, financial considerations are not the primary motivators for building energy renovations. crossCert found that the marketing of EPCs should prioritise the homeowner's lifecycle, consider renovation trigger points, deliver inspiring messages, and provide easy-to-understand visual information. This should be supported by reliable, long-term information from governments, scientific and consumer organisations, as well as free or low-cost energy renovation advice.

Related to the communication campaigns, **Deliverable 5.5 ("Towards People-Centered EPCs: Guidelines and Recommendations for the Development of People-Centered EPCs and Services")** includes an infographic on EPC promotion and marketing, mapping crossCert's approach to promoting and marketing EPCs and related initiatives.

2.9 Dissemination of the results

The dissemination of crossCert results has been significant. The table below (Table 2) presents provisional results regarding the individuals and organisations crossCert has reached in its efforts to share its outputs. Please note that these figures are still preliminary, as the project has not yet concluded. In addition to the dissemination results presented in Table 2, it should be noted that the number of people reached through social media was 40697.

Table 2. Stakeholders (and their profile) reached by the dissemination of crossCert results

Dissemination results		
KPI name	KPI goal	KPI current number
Building owners	200	144
Certification bodies	20	66
Citizens (General Public)	1000	3398
Energy Agencies	70	189
Energy Auditors	500	234
EPC Issuers	500	387
Financing providers	100	70
Professionals in the construction sector	250	170
Public authorities	250	2068
Researchers	300	388
Sectoral associations	50	1084

Furthermore, a professionally edited document summarising the main results of crossCert is currently being prepared. This document will be widely disseminated, particularly to the relevant authorities in each country responsible for designing building certification procedures.

Another key element that will enhance the dissemination of crossCert results, as well as those from other projects in the Next-Gen EPC Cluster, is the Knowledge Exchange Centre, which is nearing completion. The promotion of this platform will primarily occur in the final month of the project, and it is expected to make a significant impact. The Knowledge Exchange Centre will remain active after the project concludes and will be updated with findings from other projects. Consequently, its impact will be maintained beyond the lifespan of crossCert.

The Next-Gen EPC Cluster will also play a crucial role in promoting the results after the project ends. Furthermore, the future exploitation of the knowledge and results generated by crossCert during the project will help their dissemination. New projects may emerge as a continuation of crossCert, and partners involved in crossCert will certainly participate in national and international projects, many of which will build on the experiences gained through crossCert and help spread its findings.

In conclusion, the dissemination of crossCert results has been considerable, reaching a substantial audience within the EPC community across Europe. This effort is expected to persist beyond the project's duration, thanks to the Knowledge Exchange Centre and the ongoing use of the results.

2.10 Estimated impacts

crossCert has generated a substantial amount of information—including analyses, guidelines, recommendations, best practices, and platform tools—that supports the EPC community in enhancing various aspects of certification, as outlined in Table 3. Presumably, this information will support the design of the next generation of energy certificates and the implementation of the EPBD Recast.

In recent years, national legislation concerning energy certification in European Union countries has remained relatively stable. This stability is due to the need for consistency in national energy certification methodologies; frequent changes can lead to rejection from the EPC community. Additionally, many EU countries were awaiting the EPBD Recast to implement updates and ensure compliance with the EPBD Recast requirements.

With the publication of the EPBD Recast, most countries will need to modify aspects of their energy certification systems. Therefore, the results and analyses provided by crossCert can assist relevant authorities in designing the implementation of these required changes. Significant efforts have been made to disseminate these findings, ensuring that the EPC community across many EU nations is informed about crossCert's outcomes.

The insights, recommendations, and guidelines produced by crossCert, which contribute to impacts 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, and 10, have been shared throughout the project with the EPC community in the countries represented by crossCert partners: Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Greece, Malta, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and the UK. According to updated data (2020) from the Building Stock Observatory¹, the total area of the building stock in these countries' accounts for 38.5% of the total building stock in the EU27 and the UK. We consider this percentage to be the quantification of crossCert's contribution to impacts 03 through 10.

In the five years following the project's conclusion, we foresee that the results will reach the EPC community in additional countries, including Germany (with support from Climate Alliance, a crossCert partner), Portugal, France, and Italy, which have several organisations involved in the Next-Gen EPC Cluster. Including these nations will bring the crossCert's contribution to impacts 03-10 to 84% of the building stock (in terms of usable area) of the EU27 and the UK. By engaging with the EPC communities in Germany and Portugal, the impact objectives outlined in the Grant Agreement will be met.

In conclusion, the impacts of crossCert in the categories displayed in Table 2 have been met as per the Grant Agreement throughout the project's duration, and we estimate that these impacts will be achieved without significant issues in the five years following the project's end.

¹ <https://building-stock-observatory.energy.ec.europa.eu/database/>

Table 3. Estimated impacts of crossCert

Estimated Impacts				
Number	Impact	Quantification		Measurement unit
		Within project duration	5 years after project end	
03	Increased convergence of good quality and reliable energy performance assessment and certification and uptake and compliance with EU Directives and related standards	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU27 and the UK) under public authorities using crossCert results
04	Increased rate of application and compliance of EPCs and independent control systems with the provisions of EU and national legislation, in a defined region	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU27 and the UK) under public authorities using crossCert results
05	Increased convergence of training requirements and certification procedures for experts working on EPCs	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU27 and the UK) under public authorities using crossCert results
06	Increased integration of inspections and energy audits in the EPCs	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU27 and the UK) under public authorities using crossCert results
07	Reduction of the performance gap	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU27 and the UK) under public authorities using crossCert results
08	Additional market value of the building (single unit) with better EPC class	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU27 and the UK) under public authorities using crossCert results
10	Contribution to the implementation of the new Energy Performance Directive for Buildings and to the concepts of next-gen EPCs	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU27 and the UK) under public authorities using crossCert results

3 Impact on the energy renovation of buildings

3.1 Methodology and results

This section provides an estimation of the impacts of crossCert on the following indicators:

1. Primary Energy Savings (PES) triggered by the project.
2. Investments in Sustainable Energy driven by the project.
3. Jobs Generated as a result of the project.

All results from crossCert aim to enhance the next generation of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and support the implementation of the EPBD recast. These policy instruments will promote energy-efficient building renovations, ultimately leading to primary energy savings and increased investments.

The methodology for estimating the impact of crossCert on these three indicators involves three steps:

1. The creation of a plausible scenario for energy renovations during the project's execution and the subsequent years.
2. The assessment of the influence of the next generation of EPCs and the proper implementation of the EPBD provisions on the energy renovation of buildings.
3. The evaluation of the crossCert contribution to the successful development of the next generation of energy certificates and the implementation of the EPBD recast provisions.

As a result, we obtain the primary energy savings, investments and jobs generated that can be attributed to the crossCert outcomes.

To develop this scenario, we have relied on the EPBD recast, particularly **Article 9**, which addresses minimum energy performance standards for non-residential buildings and sets trajectories for the progressive renovation of the residential building stock.

Regarding the residential sector, the article states that Member States must ensure the following regarding the average primary energy use (measured in kWh/(m².y) of their entire residential building stock:

- (a) There should be a decrease of at least 16% compared to 2020 levels by the year 2030.
- (b) There should be a decrease of at least 20-22% compared to 2020 levels by the year 2035.
- (c) By 2040, and every five years thereafter, the average primary energy use must be equal to or less than the nationally determined value derived from a progressive decrease in average primary energy use from 2030 to 2050, in line with the goal of transforming the residential building stock into a zero-emission building stock.

For the non-residential sector, the article states the following: each Member State shall set a maximum energy performance threshold to the effect that 16% of its national non-residential building stock is above that threshold (the '16% threshold'). Each Member State shall also set a maximum energy performance threshold to the effect that 26% of its national non-residential building stock is above that threshold (the '26% threshold'). Member States may set the maximum energy performance thresholds with reference to the national non-residential building stock as a whole or per building type or category of building. Member States may set the thresholds at a level corresponding to a specific energy performance class, provided that they comply with the third subparagraph.

The minimum energy performance standards shall ensure, at least, that all non-residential buildings are below:

- (a) the 16% threshold from 2030; and
- (b) the 26% threshold from 2033.

The targets set by the EPBD recast are used to establish the building energy renovation trajectories that will shape the scenario for determining the impacts of crossCert. The input data needed to calculate the building energy renovation scenario includes the following:

- Useful area of buildings, both in the residential and non-residential sectors. Data for crossCert partner countries have been obtained from the Building Stock Observatory² and an EC report³ about building energy renovation across Europe. Figure 1 shows this data.

Figure 1. Useful floor area for residential and non-residential buildings for crossCert partner countries

- Building energy renovation rates, both in the residential and non-residential sectors. Data for crossCert partner countries have been obtained from the Building Stock Observatory² and an EC report³ about building energy renovation across Europe. The building renovations rates are characterised as: light energy renovation (around 13% of primary energy savings), medium energy renovations (around 41% of PES) and deep energy renovations (PES higher than 66%. Figure 2 shows this data for both residential and non-residential sector in each crossCert partner country.
- Primary energy savings by each renovation type, both relative (%) and absolute (kWh/m²/y) for the residential and non-residential sector in each crossCert partner country. This data has been obtained from Anne Esser et al³. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show this data.
- Investment by each renovation type (€/m²) for the residential and non-residential sector in each crossCert partner country. This data has been obtained from Anne Esser et al³. Figure 5 show this data.

² <https://building-stock-observatory.energy.ec.europa.eu/database/>

³ Anne Esser, Andreas Hermelink et al. European Commission: Comprehensive study of building energy renovation activities and the uptake of nearly zero-energy building in the EU

Figure 2. Building energy renovation rates in crossCert partner countries for both the residential and non-residential sectors

Figure 3. Relative primary energy savings in crossCert partner countries for both the residential and non-residential sectors

Figure 4. Absolute primary energy savings in crossCert partner countries for both the residential and non-residential sectors

Figure 5. Investment by renovation type in crossCert partner countries for both the residential and non-residential sectors

To set the EPBD scenario, the building renovation rates have been adjusted to align with the targets outlined in the EPBD recast for 2030. The assumed renovation rates for residential and non-residential sectors are presented below. Notably, the weighted energy renovation rate is expected to double from 2021 to 2030 in both sectors. This finding is consistent with other studies^{4,5,6,7} that indicate the current renovation rates need to be doubled or even tripled to meet the EU climate neutrality targets for 2050.

⁴ Directorate-General for internal policies. Boosting building renovation: what potential and value for Europe? Study for the ITRE Committee, 2016

⁵ Anne Esser, Andreas Hermelink et al. European Commission: Comprehensive study of building energy renovation activities and the uptake of nearly zero-energy building in the EU

⁶ BPIE. Scaling up deep energy renovation. Unleashing the potential through innovation & industrialisation. 2016.

⁷ EURIMA report. Renovation tracks for Europe up to 2050. Building renovation in Europe - What are the choices. 2012

Figure 6 shows the building renovation rates (trajectories) assumed. In the EPBD scenario, building renovation rates are expected to remain constant until 2023. From 2024, following the boost from the EPBD recast, these rates will increase, particularly concerning deep renovation.

With these renovation rates, a cumulative relative savings in primary energy of 16% is achieved in the residential sector, which aligns with the objectives of the EPBD recast. In the non-residential sector, a cumulative savings of 24% is achieved, which is also aligned with EPBD recast objectives. Specifically for non-residential buildings, it is required that the minimum energy performance standards be set below the current threshold of 16%. This means renovating the 16% of non-residential buildings that have the highest energy consumption. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that, on average, the savings in primary energy will exceed 16% since the focus will be on the buildings with the highest energy usage.

Figure 6. Assumed building renovation rates for the EPBD scenario

Figure 7. Cumulative primary energy savings (%) obtained with the building renovation rates assumed

The cumulative primary energy savings are calculated adding the annual primary energy savings, calculated as follows:

$$RPES_{ry} = [RPES_{rL} \cdot R_{rLy} + RPES_{rM} \cdot R_{rMy} + RPES_{rD} \cdot R_{rDy}]_{\square}$$

$$RPES_{nry} = [RPES_{nrL} \cdot R_{nrLy} + RPES_{nrM} \cdot R_{nrMy} + RPES_{nrD} \cdot R_{nrDy}]_{\square}$$

where:

- $RPES_{ry}$, $RPES_{nry}$ are the relative primary energy savings in the residential sector and the relative primary energy savings in the non-residential sector in year y , respectively;
- $RPES_{rL}$, $RPES_{rM}$, $RPES_{rD}$ are the averaged (in crossCert countries) relative primary energy savings per year in the residential sector achieved with light, medium and deep building renovation, respectively.
- $RPES_{nrL}$, $RPES_{nrM}$, $RPES_{nrD}$ are the averaged (in crossCert countries) relative primary energy savings per year in the non-residential sector achieved with light, medium and deep building renovation, respectively.
- R_{rLy} , R_{rMy} , R_{rDy} are the light, medium and deep building renovation rates in year y assumed for the residential sector.
- R_{nrLy} , R_{nrMy} , R_{nrDy} are the light, medium and deep building renovation rates in year y assumed for the non-residential sector.

After creating the EPBD scenario, we calculate the absolute savings in primary energy and the investments required to achieve these savings. The following equations are then applied for the calculation of the absolute primary energy savings:

$$PES_{ry} = m^2_r \cdot [PES_{rL} \cdot R_{rLy} + PES_{rM} \cdot R_{rMy} + PES_{rD} \cdot R_{rDy}]_{\square}$$

$$PES_{nry} = m^2_{nr} \cdot [PES_{nrL} \cdot R_{nrLy} + PES_{nrM} \cdot R_{nrMy} + PES_{nrD} \cdot R_{nrDy}]_{\square}$$

$$PES_{ty} = PES_{ry} + PES_{nry}$$

where:

- $PES_{ty}, PES_{ry}, PES_{nry}$ are the total primary energy savings, the primary energy savings in the residential sector and the primary energy savings in the non-residential sector in year y , respectively.
- m^2_r, m^2_{nr} are the building stock area in the crossCert countries in the residential sector (9.3 billion m^2) and in the non-residential sector (4.2 billion m^2).
- $PES_{rL}, PES_{rM}, PES_{rD}$ are the averaged (in crossCert countries) specific primary energy savings per year in the residential sector achieved with light, medium and deep building renovation, respectively. These values are, respectively, 16.4 kWh/ m^2y , 56.6 kWh/ m^2y and 108.1 kWh/ m^2y .
- $PES_{nrL}, PES_{nrM}, PES_{nrD}$ are the averaged (in crossCert countries) specific primary energy savings per year in the non-residential sector achieved with light, medium and deep building renovation, respectively. These values are, respectively, 40.4 kWh/ m^2y , 97.4 kWh/ m^2y and 145.9 kWh/ m^2y .
- $R_{rLy}, R_{rMy}, R_{rDy}$ are the light, medium and deep building renovation rates in year y assumed for the residential sector.
- $R_{nrLy}, R_{nrMy}, R_{nrDy}$ are the light, medium and deep building renovation rates in year y assumed for the non-residential sector.

To determine the investment required in the EPBD scenario described above, the following equations are applied:

$$\begin{aligned}
 IES_{ry} &= m^2_r \cdot [IES_{rL} \cdot R_{rLy} + IES_{rM} \cdot R_{rMy} + IES_{rD} \cdot R_{rDy}] \\
 IES_{nry} &= m^2_{nr} \cdot [IES_{nrL} \cdot R_{nrLy} + IES_{nrM} \cdot R_{nrMy} + IES_{nrD} \cdot R_{nrDy}] \\
 IES_{ty} &= IES_{ry} + IES_{nry}
 \end{aligned}$$

where

- $IES_{ty}, IES_{ry}, IES_{nry}$ are the total investment in sustainable energy (€), the investment in sustainable energy in the residential sector and the investment in sustainable energy in the non-residential sector in year y , respectively.
- $IES_{rL}, IES_{rM}, IES_{rD}$ are the average (in crossCert countries) specific investment in the residential sector for light, medium and deep building renovation, respectively. These values are, respectively, 92.7 €/m², 145.4 €/m²y and 207.5 €/m²y.
- $IES_{nrL}, IES_{nrM}, IES_{nrD}$ are the average (in crossCert countries) specific investment in the non-residential sector achieved with light, medium and deep building renovation, respectively. These values are, respectively, 99.6 €/m², 158.5 €/m² and 190.3 €/m²y.

The results of the EPBD scenario are compared with the BAU (Business As Usual) scenario, where 2021 building renovation rates are assumed to remain stagnant until 2030. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show cumulative energy savings and investments for the BAU and EPBD scenarios from 2021 to 2030 in the residential and non-residential sectors.

Figure 8. Cumulative primary energy savings in the residential and non-residential sector in the BAU and EPBD scenarios

Figure 9. Cumulative investment in the residential and non-residential sector in the BAU and EPBD scenarios

The impact of crossCert is determined by comparing BAU scenario with the EPBD scenario. The results from crossCert will contribute to the development of the next generation of energy performance certificates (EPCs) and to the implementation of specific provisions from the EPBD recast. The next generation of EPCs will be crucial in achieving the building renovation rates outlined in the EPBD scenario. Furthermore, the implementation of the EPBD recast is essential for reaching these renovation rates as well.

Given this context, we have estimated an attribution factor for the primary energy savings (PES) achieved within the EPBD scenario. To do this, we primarily focused on the influence that the next generation of EPCs will have in promoting energy renovation in buildings. Currently, the impact of existing EPC schemes appears to be limited⁸. Surveys indicate that only 18% of building owners in the UK and 10% in the Netherlands were influenced by information from EPCs. Based on these findings, we have assumed a current value of 20% for this parameter. In the coming years, as existing certificates transition to the next generation of EPCs, we anticipate that their influence on promoting energy renovation will increase.

Additionally, considering the number of projects, particularly those in the Next-Gen EPC Cluster, which are focused on developing the next generation of EPCs, we estimate that the crossCert attribution to the development of the next generation of EPCs is around 10%.

Considering all these assumptions, we derive the attribution factor (see Table 4) for crossCert concerning the PES and investments linked to the EPBD scenario.

Table 4. crossCert attribution factor

2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
0	0	0	0.020	0.023	0.025	0.028	0.031	0.033

Multiplying the attribution factor by the difference between the primary energy savings in the BAU scenario and the EPBD scenario, we obtain the PES triggered by crossCert. The annual PES triggered by crossCert within the project duration are estimated at 93 GWh/y, and in the long term, at 826 GWh/y (see Table 5).

Table 5. Primary energy savings triggered by crossCert (GWh/y)

2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
0	0	0	114	200	320	472	649	826

Multiplying the attribution factor by the difference between the investment in the EPBD scenario and the BAU scenario, we obtain the investments triggered by crossCert. The investment triggered by crossCert within the project duration is estimated at 194 million Euro per year, and in the long term, at 1,608 million Euro per year (see Table 6). According to these figures, the accumulated investment triggered by the crossCert results would be 5,035 million Euro.

Table 6. Investments triggered by crossCert (million €)

2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
0	0	0	194	403	633	928	1269	1608

In terms of job creation, we consider that every million Euros invested in the energy renovation of buildings generates 18 jobs. This figure is based on a report⁹ from the Buildings Performance Institute Europe (BPIE), which reviewed 35 research studies. By applying this data to the estimated investment triggered by crossCert, we estimate an impact of 3,497 jobs during the project duration and 90,634 jobs within five years following the project's completion.

The impacts achieved are generally consistent with those outlined in the Grand Agreement, although they are slightly lower than anticipated, particularly during the project's execution. Nevertheless, the uncertainty in the impacts is high. The methodology used for calculating impacts includes factors such as the attribution factor and the building renovation rates, where even small changes can significantly influence the results. It must be noted that the impacts (PES, investments, and jobs generated) have been calculated only in the crossCert partners' countries. However, it is important to note that the outcomes

⁸ Y. Li et al. Review of building energy performance certification schemes towards future improvement. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 113, ISSN 1364-0321, 2019

⁹ BPIE. Building renovation: A kick-starter for the EU recovery <https://www.renovate-europe.eu/2020/06/10/building-renovation-a-kick-starter-for-the-eu-economy/>

from crossCert may also have an impact on other European countries once the project is completed. Therefore, the final impacts may be higher than those presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Estimated impacts of crossCert

Estimated Impacts				
Number	Impact	Quantification		Measurement unit
		Within project duration	5 years after project end	
01	Primary energy savings triggered by the project	114	826	GWh/year
02	Investments in sustainable energy triggered by the project	194	5035	million EUR
09	Jobs generated	3497	90634	Number of full-time equivalent jobs

4 Conclusion

This report presents the estimated impacts of crossCert, detailing both the methodology used for estimation and the values obtained. Table 8 compares the achieved impacts versus the expected impacts. A reasonable agreement between both impacts is observed.

There are two primary types of impacts: those focused on enhancing energy certification methodologies and those related to promoting the energy renovation of buildings. The estimated values for both types of impacts are consistent with the expectations stated in the Grant Agreement.

In terms of improving energy certification methodologies, crossCert has produced a wealth of results, guidelines, insights, recommendations, and tools that will be available to the EPC community in each participating country. These resources are intended to support the improvement of energy certification methodologies. Furthermore, crossCert has yielded outcomes that can support Public Administrations in implementing the new provisions of the EPBD recast.

The impacts associated with promoting building renovation have been evaluated based on a scenario of energy building renovations that align with the EPBD recast. This assessment considers the contribution of crossCert in realising that scenario.

We anticipate a greater impact in the coming years once the project is completed. Modifications to EPC methodologies in the countries involved in crossCert have been relatively minor during the project's execution. However, we expect more significant changes in the near future due to the necessity of implementing the new provisions of the EPBD recast. The results from crossCert will be particularly valuable for designing the changes in the national certification methodologies.

Table 8. Expected impacts versus achieved impacts

Expected Impacts (GA) versus achieved impacts						
Number	Impact	Expected impacts		Achieved impacts		Measurement unit
		Within project duration	5 years after project end	Within project duration	5 years after project end	
01	Primary energy savings triggered by the project	165.0	735.0	114.0	826.0	GWh/year
02	Investments in sustainable energy triggered by the project	364	5733	194	5035	million EUR
03	Increased convergence of good quality and reliable energy performance assessment and certification and uptake and compliance with EU Directives and related standards	37.0	60.0	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
04	Increased rate of application and compliance of EPCs and independent control systems with the provisions of EU and national legislation, in a defined region	37.0	60.0	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
05	Increased convergence of training requirements and certification procedures for experts working on EPCs	37.0	60.0	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
06	Increased integration of inspections and energy audits in the EPCs	37.0	60.0	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
07	Reduction of the performance gap	37.0	60.0	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
08	Additional market value of the building (single unit) with better EPC class	37.0	60.0	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results
09	Jobs generated	6552	103194	3497	90634	Number of full-time equivalent jobs
10	Contribution to the implementation of the new Energy Performance on Buildings Directive and to the concepts of next-gen EPCs	37.0	60.0	38.5	84.0	% building stock (EU28) under public authorities using crossCert results